

Universal and Upside-down Magic Cubes

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For complete work access the author's web-site links:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=12875>

Abstract

*This work brings magic cubes in **universal** or **upside-down** way. It is based on 6 magic squares for six sides of the cube. By **upside-down**, we understand that making 180° rotation still we have a magic square. By **mirror looking**, we understand that putting magic square in front of mirror, still we get a magic square. When the magic square is of both type, i.e., **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, we call it as **universal** magic square. In case of **upside-down** situation, then 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6. In case of mirror looking, the numbers 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2 (writing as **digital fonts**. The work is only for the magic squares of orders 3, 4, 5, 7 and 8. Whole work can be accessed at author's web-site as given above.*

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1 Introduction

This work bring magic cubes with six sides as magic squares of orders 3, 4, 5, 7 to 8. Most of the magic squares are with different magic sums. These examples brings only **universal** and or **upside-down** magic cubes. By **universal** we understand that when the magic square is 180° rotatable and are **mirror looking**, while in case of **upside-down** the magic squares are only 180° rotatable. n case of **upside-down** situation, then 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6. In case of mirror looking, the numbers 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2 (writing as **digital fonts**. For the general case for the orders 3 to 10, see the author's another work [107].

For more studies on magic cubes refer to C. Boyer [1], O.A. Dawood, et al. [2], B. Golunski [3], W. Trump [4, 5], W. Walkington [6] and A. Winkel [8].

2 Universal and Upside-down Magic Cubes of Order 3

2.1 Upside-down Magic Cube

Example 2.1. *Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 3:*

6619	9196	1961	1616	6191	9969	9611	1199	6966
9966	1611	6199	6961	9619	1196	1969	6616	9191
1191	6969	9616	9199	1966	6611	6196	9961	1619
9611	1199	6966	1996	6661	9119	9991	1669	6116
1969	6616	9191	6111	9999	1666	1119	6996	9661
6196	9961	1619	9669	1116	6991	6666	9111	1999

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 3-digits, 1, 6 and 9. All the blocks of order 3×3 are **semi-magic** with equal **semi-magic** sums, i.e.,

$$S_{3 \times 3}(1) = S_{3 \times 3}(2) = S_{3 \times 3}(3) = S_{3 \times 3}(4) = S_{3 \times 3}(5) = S_{3 \times 3}(6) := 17776.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

			6619	9196	1961
			9966	1611	6199
			1191	6969	9616
9611	1199	6966	1616	6191	9969
1969	6616	9191	6961	9619	1196
6196	9961	1619	9199	1966	6611

Back

9611	1199	6966	1996	6661	9119
1969	6616	9191	6111	9999	1666
6196	9961	1619	9669	1116	6991
9991	1669	6116			
1119	6996	9661			
6666	9111	1999			

Above magic cube is **upside-down**, i.e., each face is 180° rotatable.

Example 2.2. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 3:

2205	5052	0520	0202	2050	5525	5200	0055	2522
5522	0200	2055	2520	5205	0052	0525	2202	5050
0050	2525	5202	5055	0522	2200	2052	5520	0205
5200	0055	2522	0552	2220	5005	5550	0225	2002
0525	2202	5050	2000	5555	0222	0005	2552	5220
2052	5520	0205	5225	0002	2550	2222	5000	0555

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 3-digits, 1, 6 and 9. All the blocks of order 3×3 are **semi-magic** with equal **semi-magic** sums, i.e.,

$$S_{3 \times 3}(1) = S_{3 \times 3}(2) = S_{3 \times 3}(3) = S_{3 \times 3}(4) = S_{3 \times 3}(5) = S_{3 \times 3}(6) := 25553.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

			2205	5052	0520
			5522	0200	2055
			0050	2525	5202
5200	0055	2522	0202	2050	5525
0525	2202	5050	2520	5205	0052
2052	5520	0205	5055	0522	2200

Back

5200	0055	2522	0552	2220	5005
0525	2202	5050	2000	5555	0222
2052	5520	0205	5225	0002	2550
5550	0225	2002			
0005	2552	5220			
2222	5000	0555			

Above magic cube is **upside-down**, i.e, each face is 180° rotatable.

2.2 Universal Magic Cube

Example 2.3. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 3:

2285	5852	8528	8282	2858	5525	5288	8855	2522
5522	8288	2855	2528	5285	8852	8525	2282	5858
8858	2525	5282	5855	8522	2288	2852	5528	8285
5288	8855	2522	8552	2228	5885	5558	8225	2882
8525	2282	5858	2888	5555	8222	8885	2552	5228
2852	5528	8285	5225	8882	2558	2222	5888	8555

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 3-digits, 2, 5 and 8. All the blocks of order 3×3 are **semi-magic** with equal **semi-magic** sums, i.e.,

$$S_{3 \times 3}(1) = S_{3 \times 3}(2) = S_{3 \times 3}(3) = S_{3 \times 3}(4) = S_{3 \times 3}(5) = S_{3 \times 3}(6) := 16665.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

			2285	5852	8528
			5522	8288	2855
			8858	2525	5282
5288	8855	2522	8282	2858	5525
8525	2282	5858	2528	5285	8852
2852	5528	8285	5855	8522	2288

Back

5288	8855	2522	8552	2228	5885
8525	2282	5858	2888	5555	8222
2852	5528	8285	5225	8882	2558
5558	8225	2882			
8885	2552	5228			
2222	5888	8555			

Above magic cube is readable in any position, i.e., each face is **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

Example 2.4. Let's consider following six magic squares of order 3:

6689	9896	8968	8686	6898	9969	9688	8899	6966
9966	8688	6899	6968	9689	8896	8969	6686	9898
8898	6969	9686	9899	8966	6688	6896	9968	8689
9688	8899	6966	8996	6668	9889	9998	8669	6886
8969	6686	9898	6888	9999	8666	8889	6996	9668
6896	9968	8689	9669	8886	6998	6666	9888	8999

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 3-digits, 0, 2 and 5. All the blocks of order 3×3 are **semi-magic** with equal **semi-magic** sums, i.e.,

$$S_{3 \times 3}(1) = S_{3 \times 3}(2) = S_{3 \times 3}(3) = S_{3 \times 3}(4) = S_{3 \times 3}(5) = S_{3 \times 3}(6) := 7777.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

			6689	9896	8968
			9966	8688	6899
			8898	6969	9686
9688	8899	6966	8686	6898	9969
8969	6686	9898	6968	9689	8896
6896	9968	8689	9899	8966	6688

Back

9688	8899	6966	8996	6668	9889
8969	6686	9898	6888	9999	8666
6896	9968	8689	9669	8886	6998
9998	8669	6886			
8889	6996	9668			
6666	9888	8999			

Above magic cube is readable in any position, i.e., each face is **upside-down** and/or **mirror looking**.

3 Universal and Upside-down Magic Cubes of Order 4

3.1 Upside-down Magic Cube

Example 3.1. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 4:

1111	8686	9898	6969	1668	8199	9981	6816	1889	8918	9166	6691
9869	6998	1186	8611	9916	6881	1699	8168	9191	6666	1818	8989
6986	9811	8669	1198	6899	9968	8116	1681	6618	9189	8991	1866
8698	1169	6911	9886	8181	1616	6868	9999	8966	1891	6689	9118
1996	8861	9619	6188	1896	8961	9119	6688	1989	8818	9666	6191
9688	6119	1961	8896	9188	6619	1861	8996	9691	6166	1918	8889
6161	9696	8888	1919	6661	9196	8988	1819	6118	9689	8891	1966
8819	1988	6196	9661	8919	1888	6696	9161	8866	1991	6189	9618

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 4-digits, 1, 6, 8 and 9. All the blocks of order 4x4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{4 \times 4}(1) = S_{4 \times 4}(2) = S_{4 \times 4}(3) = S_{4 \times 4}(4) = S_{4 \times 4}(5) = S_{4 \times 4}(6) := 26664.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

				1111	8686	9898	6969
				9869	6998	1186	8611
				6986	9811	8669	1198
				8698	1169	6911	9886
1889	8918	9166	6691	1668	8199	9981	6816
9191	6666	1818	8989	9916	6881	1699	8168
6618	9189	8991	1866	6899	9968	8116	1681
8966	1891	6689	9118	8181	1616	6868	9999

Back

1996	8861	9619	6188	1896	8961	9119	6688
9688	6119	1961	8896	9188	6619	1861	8996
6161	9696	8888	1919	6661	9196	8988	1819
8819	1988	6196	9661	8919	1888	6696	9161
1989	8818	9666	6191				
9691	6166	1918	8889				
6118	9689	8891	1966				
8866	1991	6189	9618				

Above magic cube is **upside-down**, i.e., each face is 180° rotatable.

3.2 Universal Magic Cubes

Example 3.2. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 4:

1111	8282	5858	2525	1228	8155	5581	2812	1885	8518	5122	2251
5825	2558	1182	8211	5512	2881	1255	8128	5151	2222	1818	8585
2582	5811	8225	1158	2855	5528	8112	1281	2218	5185	8551	1822
8258	1125	2511	5882	8181	1212	2828	5555	8522	1851	2285	5118
1552	8821	5215	2188	1852	8521	5115	2288	1585	8818	5222	2151
5288	2115	1521	8852	5188	2215	1821	8552	5251	2122	1518	8885
2121	5252	8888	1515	2221	5152	8588	1815	2118	5285	8851	1522
8815	1588	2152	5221	8515	1888	2252	5121	8822	1551	2185	5218

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 4-digits, 1, 2, 5 and 8. All the blocks of order 4×4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{4 \times 4}(1) = S_{4 \times 4}(2) = S_{4 \times 4}(3) = S_{4 \times 4}(4) = S_{4 \times 4}(5) = S_{4 \times 4}(6) := 17776.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

1111	8282	5858	2525
5825	2558	1182	8211
2582	5811	8225	1158
8258	1125	2511	5882
1885	8518	5122	2251
5151	2222	1818	8585
2218	5185	8551	1822
8522	1851	2285	5118
1228	8155	5581	2812
5512	2881	1255	8128
2855	5528	8112	1281
8181	1212	2828	5555

Back

1552	8821	5215	2188	1852	8521	5115	2288
5288	2115	1521	8852	5188	2215	1821	8552
2121	5252	8888	1515	2221	5152	8588	1815
8815	1588	2152	5221	8515	1888	2252	5121
1585	8818	5222	2151				
5251	2122	1518	8885				
2118	5285	8851	1522				
8822	1551	2185	5218				

Above magic cube is **universal**, i.e., each face is **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

Example 3.3. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 4:

0000	8282	5858	2525	0228	8055	5580	2802	0885	8508	5022	2250
5825	2558	0082	8200	5502	2880	0255	8028	5050	2222	0808	8585
2582	5800	8225	0058	2855	5528	8002	0280	2208	5085	8550	0822
8258	0025	2500	5882	8080	0202	2828	5555	8522	0850	2285	5008
0552	8820	5205	2088	0852	8520	5005	2288	0585	8808	5222	2050
5288	2005	0520	8852	5088	2205	0820	8552	5250	2022	0508	8885
2020	5252	8888	0505	2220	5052	8588	0805	2008	5285	8850	0522
8805	0588	2052	5220	8505	0888	2252	5020	8822	0550	2085	5208

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 4-digits, 0, 2, 5 and 8. All the blocks of order 4×4 are magic squares with equal magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{4 \times 4}(1) = S_{4 \times 4}(2) = S_{4 \times 4}(3) = S_{4 \times 4}(4) = S_{4 \times 4}(5) = S_{4 \times 4}(6) := 16665.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

				0000	8282	5858	2525
				5825	2558	0082	8200
				2582	5800	8225	0058
				8258	0025	2500	5882
0885	8508	5022	2250	0228	8055	5580	2802
5050	2222	0808	8585	5502	2880	0255	8028
2208	5085	8550	0822	2855	5528	8002	0280
8522	0850	2285	5008	8080	0202	2828	5555

Back

0552	8820	5205	2088	0852	8520	5005	2288
5288	2005	0520	8852	5088	2205	0820	8552
2020	5252	8888	0505	2220	5052	8588	0805
8805	0588	2052	5220	8505	0888	2252	5020
0585	8808	5222	2050				
5250	2022	0508	8885				
2008	5285	8850	0522				
8822	0550	2085	5208				

Above magic cube is **universal**, i.e., each face is **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

4 Universal and Upside-down Magic Cubes of Order 5

4.1 Upside-down Magic Cube

Example 4.1. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 5:

1618	6889	6966	9198	9681	1919	6188	8661	8899	9986	1816	6691	8168	8996	9869
9166	9698	1681	6818	6989	8861	9999	1986	6119	8688	8968	9896	1869	6616	8191
6881	6918	9189	9666	1698	6186	8619	8888	9961	1999	6669	8116	8991	9868	1896
9689	1666	6898	6981	9118	9988	1961	6199	8686	8819	9891	1868	6696	8169	8916
6998	9181	9618	1689	6866	8699	8886	9919	1988	6161	8196	8969	9816	1891	6668
1916	6191	8668	8896	9969	1818	6689	8166	8998	9881	1619	6888	6961	9199	9686
8868	9996	1969	6116	8691	8966	9898	1881	6618	8189	9161	9699	1686	6819	6988
6169	8616	8891	9968	1996	6681	8118	8989	9866	1898	6886	6919	9188	9661	1699
9991	1968	6196	8669	8816	9889	1866	6698	8181	8918	9688	1661	6899	6986	9119
8696	8869	9916	1991	6168	8198	8981	9818	1889	6666	6999	9186	9619	1688	6861

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 4-digits, 0, 2, 5 and 8. All the blocks of order 5×5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{5 \times 5}(1) := 15953, S_{5 \times 5}(2) := 25250, S_{5 \times 5}(3) := 25457, S_{5 \times 5}(4) := 25157, S_{5 \times 5}(5) := 25553 \text{ and } S_{5 \times 5}(6) := 25553.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

1618	6889	6966	9198	9681					
9166	9698	1681	6818	6989					
6881	6918	9189	9666	1698					
9689	1666	6898	6981	9118					
6998	9181	9618	1689	6866					
1816	6691	8168	8996	9869	1919	6188	8661	8899	9986
8968	9896	1869	6616	8191	8861	9999	1986	6119	8688
6669	8116	8991	9868	1896	6186	8619	8888	9961	1999
9891	1868	6696	8169	8916	9988	1961	6199	8686	8819
8196	8969	9816	1891	6668	8699	8886	9919	1988	6161

Back

1916	6191	8668	8896	9969	1619	6888	6961	9199	9686
8868	9996	1969	6116	8691	9161	9699	1686	6819	6988
6169	8616	8891	9968	1996	6886	6919	9188	9661	1699
9991	1968	6196	8669	8816	9688	1661	6899	6986	9119
8696	8869	9916	1991	6168	6999	9186	9619	1688	6861
1818	6689	8166	8998	9881					
8966	9898	1881	6618	8189					
6681	8118	8989	9866	1898					
9889	1866	6698	8181	8918					
8198	8981	9818	1889	6666					

Above magic cube is **upside-down**, i.e., each face is 180° rotatable.

4.2 Universal Magic Cubes

Example 4.2. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 5:

0208	2885	2522	5058	5280	0505	2088	8220	8855	5582	0802	2250	8028	8552	5825
5022	5258	0280	2808	2585	8820	5555	0582	2005	8288	8528	5852	0825	2202	8050
2880	2508	5085	5222	0258	2082	8205	8888	5520	0555	2225	8002	8550	5828	0852
5285	0222	2858	2580	5008	5588	0520	2055	8282	8805	5850	0828	2252	8025	8502
2558	5080	5208	0285	2822	8255	8882	5505	0588	2020	8052	8525	5802	0850	2228
0502	2050	8228	8852	5525	0808	2285	8022	8558	5880	0808	2285	8022	8558	5880
8828	5552	0525	2002	8250	8522	5858	0880	2208	8085	8522	5858	0880	2208	8085
2025	8202	8850	5528	0552	2280	8008	8585	5822	858	2280	8008	8585	5822	0858
5550	0528	2052	8225	8802	5885	0822	2258	8080	8508	5885	0822	2258	8080	8508
8252	8825	5502	0550	2028	8058	8580	5808	0885	2222	8058	8580	5808	0885	2222

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 4-digits, 1, 6, 8 and 9. All the blocks of order 5×5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{5 \times 5}(1) := 34352, S_{5 \times 5}(2) := 35653, S_{5 \times 5}(3) := 35540, S_{5 \times 5}(4) := 35640, S_{5 \times 5}(5) := 35552 \text{ and } S_{5 \times 5}(6) := 34353.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

					0208	2885	2522	5058	5280
					5022	5258	0280	2808	2585
					2880	2508	5085	5222	0258
					5285	0222	2858	2580	5008
					2558	5080	5208	0285	2822
0802	2250	8028	8552	5825	0505	2088	8220	8855	5582
8528	5852	0825	2202	8050	8820	5555	0582	2005	8288
2225	8002	8550	5828	0852	2082	8205	8888	5520	0555
5850	0828	2252	8025	8502	5588	0520	2055	8282	8805
8052	8525	5802	0850	2228	8255	8882	5505	0588	2020

Back

0502	2050	8228	8852	5525	0205	2888	2520	5055	5282
8828	5552	0525	2002	8250	5020	5255	0282	2805	2588
2025	8202	8850	5528	0552	2882	2505	5088	5220	0255
5550	0528	2052	8225	8802	5288	0220	2855	2582	5005
8252	8825	5502	0550	2028	2555	5082	5205	0288	2820
0808	2285	8022	8558	5880					
8522	5858	0880	2208	8085					
2280	8008	8585	5822	0858					
5885	0822	2258	8080	8508					
8058	8580	5808	0885	2222					

Above magic cube is **universal**, i.e., each face is **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

Example 4.3. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 5:

1218	2885	2522	5158	5281	1515	2188	8221	8855	5582	1812	2251	8128	8552	5825
5122	5258	1281	2818	2585	8821	5555	1582	2115	8288	8528	5852	1825	2212	8151
2881	2518	5185	5222	1258	2182	8215	8888	5521	1555	2225	8112	8551	5828	1852
5285	1222	2858	2581	5118	5588	1521	2155	8282	8815	5851	1828	2252	8125	8512
2558	5181	5218	1285	2822	8255	8882	5515	1588	2121	8152	8525	5812	1851	2228
1512	2151	8228	8852	5525	1818	2285	8122	8558	5881	1215	2888	2521	5155	5282
8828	5552	1525	2112	8251	8522	5858	1881	2218	8185	5121	5255	1282	2815	2588
2125	8212	8851	5528	1552	2281	8118	8585	5822	1858	2882	2515	5188	5221	1255
5551	1528	2152	8225	8812	5885	1822	2258	8181	8518	5288	1221	2855	2582	5115
8252	8825	5512	1551	2128	8158	8581	5818	1885	2222	2555	5182	5215	1288	2821

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 4-digits, 1, 2, 5 and 8. All the blocks of order 5×5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{5 \times 5}(1) := 17064, S_{5 \times 5}(2) := 26361, S_{5 \times 5}(3) := 26568, S_{5 \times 5}(4) := 26268, S_{5 \times 5}(5) := 26664 \text{ and } S_{5 \times 5}(6) := 17061.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

1218	2885	2522	5158	5281
5122	5258	1281	2818	2585
2881	2518	5185	5222	1258
5285	1222	2858	2581	5118
2558	5181	5218	1285	2822
1812	2251	8128	8552	5825
8528	5852	1825	2212	8151
2225	8112	8551	5828	1852
5851	1828	2252	8125	8512
8152	8525	5812	1851	2228
1515	2188	8221	8855	5582
8821	5555	1582	2115	8288
2182	8215	8888	5521	1555
5588	1521	2155	8282	8815
8255	8882	5515	1588	2121

Back

1512	2151	8228	8852	5525	1215	2888	2521	5155	5282
8828	5552	1525	2112	8251	5121	5255	1282	2815	2588
2125	8212	8851	5528	1552	2882	2515	5188	5221	1255
5551	1528	2152	8225	8812	5288	1221	2855	2582	5115
8252	8825	5512	1551	2128	2555	5182	5215	1288	2821
1818	2285	8122	8558	5881					
8522	5858	1881	2218	8185					
2281	8118	8585	5822	1858					
5885	1822	2258	8181	8518					
8158	8581	5818	1885	2222					

Above magic cube is **universal**, i.e., each face is **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

5 Universal and Upside-down Magic Cubes of Order 7

5.1 Upside-down Magic Cubes

Example 5.1. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 7:

2525	8592	6856	5685	8658	9286	5868	2526	8596	6828	5698	8662	9288	5865	2625	9892	6556	2885	8858	9686	6268
5656	8685	9258	5886	2568	8525	6892	5628	8698	9262	5888	2565	8526	6896	2856	8885	9658	6286	2668	9825	6592
5858	2586	8568	6825	5692	8656	9285	5862	2588	8565	6826	5696	8628	9298	6258	2686	9868	6525	2892	8856	9685
6868	5625	8692	9256	5885	2558	8586	6865	5626	8696	9228	5898	2562	8588	6568	2825	8892	9656	6285	2658	9886
9292	5856	2585	8558	6886	5668	8625	9296	5828	2598	8562	6888	5665	8626	9692	6256	2685	9858	6586	868	8825
8585	6858	5686	8668	9225	5892	2556	8598	6862	5688	8665	9226	5896	2528	9885	6558	2886	8868	9625	6292	2656
8686	9268	5825	2592	8556	6885	5658	8688	9265	5826	2596	8528	6898	5662	8886	9668	6225	2692	9856	6585	2858
2529	8595	6852	5682	8659	9289	5869	2629	2852	6259	6569	9695	9882	8889	2929	8295	6952	5282	8959	9589	5969
5652	8682	9259	5889	2569	8529	6895	9895	8882	2689	2829	6252	6559	9669	5252	8982	9559	5989	2969	8229	6995
5859	2589	8569	6829	5695	8652	9282	6552	9659	9869	8895	2682	2889	6229	5959	2989	8269	6929	5295	8952	9582
6869	5629	8695	9252	5882	2559	8589	2882	6289	6529	9652	9859	8869	2695	6969	5229	8995	9552	5982	2959	8289
9295	5852	2582	8559	6889	5669	8629	8859	2669	2895	6282	6589	9629	9852	9595	5952	2982	8259	6989	5269	8929
8582	6859	5689	8669	9229	5895	2552	9689	9829	8852	2659	2869	6295	6582	8282	6959	5289	8969	9529	5995	2952
8689	9269	5829	2595	8552	6882	5659	6269	6595	9682	9889	8829	2652	2859	8989	9569	5929	2995	8252	6982	5259

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 5-digits, 0, 1, 6, 8 and 9. All the blocks of order 7×7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{7 \times 7}(1) := 36360, S_{7 \times 7}(2) := 36417, S_{7 \times 7}(3) := 42060, S_{7 \times 7}(4) := 36367, S_{7 \times 7}(5) := 42067 \text{ and } S_{7 \times 7}(6) := 37067.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

							2525	8592	6856	5685	8658	9286	5868							
							5656	8685	9258	5886	2568	8525	6892							
							5858	2586	8568	6825	5692	8656	9285							
							6868	5625	8692	9256	5885	2558	8586							
							9292	5856	2585	8558	6886	5668	8625							
							8585	6858	5686	8668	9225	5892	2556							
							8686	9268	5825	2592	8556	6885	5658							
							2625	9892	6556	885	8858	9686	6268	2526	8596	6828	5698	8662	9288	5865
							2856	8885	9658	6286	2668	9825	6592	5628	8698	9262	5888	2565	8526	6896
							6258	2686	9868	6525	2892	8856	9685	5862	2588	8565	6826	5696	8628	9298
							6568	2825	8892	9656	6285	2658	9886	6865	5626	8696	9228	5898	2562	8588
							9692	6256	2685	9858	6586	2868	8825	9296	5828	2598	8562	6888	5665	8626
							9885	6558	2886	8868	9625	6292	2656	8598	6862	5688	8665	9226	5896	2528
							8886	9668	6225	2692	9856	6585	2858	8688	9265	5826	2596	8528	6898	5662

Back

2529	8595	6852	5682	8659	9289	5869	2629	2852	6259	6569	9695	9882	8889
5652	8682	9259	5889	2569	8529	6895	9895	8882	2689	2829	6252	6559	9669
5859	2589	8569	6829	5695	8652	9282	6552	9659	9869	8895	2682	2889	6229
6869	5629	8695	9252	5882	2559	8589	2882	6289	6529	9652	9859	8869	2695
9295	5852	2582	8559	6889	5669	8629	8859	2669	2895	6282	6589	9629	9852
8582	6859	5689	8669	9229	5895	2552	9689	9829	8852	2659	2869	6295	6582
8689	9269	5829	2595	8552	6882	5659	6269	6595	9682	9889	8829	2652	2859
2929	8295	6952	5282	8959	9589	5969							
5252	8982	9559	5989	2969	8229	6995							
5959	2989	8269	6929	5295	8952	9582							
6969	5229	8995	9552	5982	2959	8289							
9595	5952	2982	8259	6989	5269	8929							
8282	6959	5289	8969	9529	5995	2952							
8989	9569	5929	2995	8252	6982	5259							

Above magic cube is **upside-down**, i.e., each face is 180° rotatable.

Example 5.2. Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 7:

0101	8190	6816	1681	8618	9086	1868	0106	8196	6808	1698	8660	9088	1861	0601	9890	6116	0881	8818	9686	6068
1616	8681	9018	1886	0168	8101	6890	1608	8698	9060	1888	0161	8106	6896	0816	8881	9618	6086	0668	9801	6190
1818	0186	8168	6801	1690	8616	9081	1860	0188	8161	6806	1696	8608	9098	6018	0686	9868	6101	0890	8816	9681
6868	1601	8690	9016	1881	0118	8186	6861	1606	8696	9008	1898	0160	8188	6168	0801	8890	9616	6081	0618	9886
9090	1816	0181	8118	6886	1668	8601	9096	1808	0198	8160	6888	1661	8606	9690	6016	0681	9818	6186	0868	8801
8181	6818	1686	8668	9001	1890	0116	8198	6860	1688	8661	9006	1896	0108	9881	6118	0886	8868	9601	6090	0616
8686	9068	1801	0190	8116	6881	1618	8688	9061	1806	0196	8108	6898	1660	8886	9668	6001	6090	9816	6181	0818
0109	8191	6810	1680	8619	9089	1869	0609	8110	6019	6169	9691	9880	8889	0909	8091	6910	1080	8919	9189	1969
1610	8680	9019	1889	0169	8109	6891	9891	8880	0689	0809	6010	6119	9669	1010	8980	9119	1989	0969	8009	6991
1819	0189	8169	6809	1691	8610	9080	6110	9619	9869	8891	0680	0889	6009	1919	0989	8069	6909	1091	8910	9180
6869	1609	8691	9010	1880	0119	8189	0880	6089	6109	9610	9819	8869	0691	6969	1009	8991	9110	1980	0919	8089
9091	1810	0180	8119	6889	1669	8609	8819	0669	0891	6080	6189	9609	9810	9191	1910	0980	8019	6989	1069	8909
8180	6819	1689	8669	9009	1891	0110	9689	9809	8810	0619	0869	6091	6180	8080	6919	1089	8969	9109	1991	0910
8689	9069	1809	0191	8110	6880	1619	6069	6191	9680	9889	8809	0610	0819	8989	9169	1909	0991	8010	6980	1019

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 5-digits, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9. All the blocks of order 7×7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{7 \times 7}(1) := 47470, S_{7 \times 7}(2) := 47463, S_{7 \times 7}(3) := 47463, S_{7 \times 7}(4) := 47475, S_{7 \times 7}(5) := 46775 \text{ and } S_{7 \times 7}(6) := 47975.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

							0101	8190	6816	1681	8618	9086	1868
							1616	8681	9018	1886	0168	8101	6890
							1818	0186	8168	6801	1690	8616	9081
							6868	1601	8690	9016	1881	0118	8186
							9090	1816	0181	8118	6886	1668	8601
							8181	6818	1686	8668	9001	1890	0116
							8686	9068	1801	0190	8116	6881	1618
0601	9890	6116	0881	8818	9686	6068	0106	8196	6808	1698	8660	9088	1861
0816	8881	9618	6086	0668	9801	6190	1608	8698	9060	1888	0161	8106	6896
6018	0686	9868	6101	0890	8816	9681	1860	0188	8161	6806	1696	8608	9098
6168	0801	8890	9616	6081	0618	9886	6861	1606	8696	9008	1898	0160	8188
9690	6016	0681	9818	6186	0868	8801	9096	1808	0198	8160	6888	1661	8606
9881	6118	0886	8868	9601	6090	0616	8198	6860	1688	8661	9006	1896	0108
8886	9668	6001	0690	9816	6181	0818	8688	9061	1806	0196	8108	6898	1660

Back

0109	8191	6810	1680	8619	9089	1869	0609	0810	6019	6169	9691	9880	8889
1610	8680	9019	1889	0169	8109	6891	9891	8880	0689	0809	6010	6119	9669
1819	0189	8169	6809	1691	8610	9080	6110	9619	9869	8891	0680	0889	6009
6869	1609	8691	9010	1880	0119	8189	0880	6089	6109	9610	9819	8869	0691
9091	1810	0180	8119	6889	1669	8609	8819	0669	0891	6080	6189	9609	9810
8180	6819	1689	8669	9009	1891	0110	9689	9809	8810	0619	0869	6091	6180
8689	9069	1809	0191	8110	6880	1619	6069	6191	9680	9889	8809	0610	0819
0909	8091	6910	1080	8919	9189	1969							
1010	8980	9119	1989	969	8009	6991							
1919	0989	8069	6909	1091	8910	9180							
6969	1009	8991	9110	1980	0919	8089							
9191	1910	0980	8019	6989	1069	8909							
8080	6919	1089	8969	9109	1991	0910							
8989	9169	1909	0991	8010	6980	1019							

Above magic cube is **universal**, i.e., each face is **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

5.2 Universal Magic Cubes

Example 5.3. *Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 7:*

0101	8150	2812	1281	8218	5082	1828	0102	8152	2808	1258	8220	5088	1821	0201	5850	2112	0881	8818	5282	2028
1212	8281	5018	1882	0128	8101	2850	1208	8258	5020	1888	0121	8102	2852	0812	8881	5218	2082	0228	5801	2150
1818	0182	8128	2801	1250	8212	5081	1820	0188	8121	2802	1252	8208	5058	2018	0282	5828	2101	0850	8812	5281
2828	1201	8250	5012	1881	0118	8182	2821	1202	8252	5008	1858	0120	8188	2128	0801	8850	5212	2081	0218	5882
5050	1812	0181	8118	2882	1228	8201	5052	1808	0158	8120	2888	1221	8202	5250	2012	0281	5818	2182	0828	8801
8181	2818	1282	8228	5001	1850	0112	8158	2820	1288	8221	5002	1852	0108	5881	2118	0882	8828	5201	2050	0212
8282	5028	1801	0150	8112	2881	1218	8288	5021	1802	0152	8108	2858	1220	8882	5228	2001	0250	5812	2181	0818
0105	8151	2810	1280	8215	5085	1825	0205	0810	2015	2125	5251	5880	8885	0505	8051	2510	1080	8515	5185	1525
1210	8280	5015	1885	0125	8105	2851	5851	8880	0285	0805	2010	2115	5225	1010	8580	5115	1585	0525	8005	2551
1815	0185	8125	2805	1251	8210	5080	2110	5215	5825	8851	0280	0885	2005	1515	0585	8025	2505	1051	8510	5180
2825	1205	8251	5010	1880	0115	8185	0880	2085	2105	5210	5815	8825	0251	2525	1005	8551	5110	1580	0515	8085
5051	1810	0180	8115	2885	1225	8205	8815	0225	0851	2080	2185	5205	5810	5151	1510	0580	8015	2585	1025	8505
8180	2815	1285	8225	5005	1851	0110	5285	5805	8810	0215	0825	2051	2180	8080	2515	1085	8525	5105	1551	0510
8285	5025	1805	0151	8110	2880	1215	2025	2151	5280	5885	8805	0210	0815	8585	5125	1505	0551	8010	2580	1015

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 4-digits, 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8. All the blocks of order 7×7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{7 \times 7}(1) := 27472, S_{7 \times 7}(2) := 27449, S_{7 \times 7}(3) := 27449, S_{7 \times 7}(4) := 27471, S_{7 \times 7}(5) := 25171 \text{ and } S_{7 \times 7}(6) := 27371.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

							0101	8150	2812	1281	8218	5082	1828
							1212	8281	5018	1882	0128	8101	2850
							1818	0182	8128	2801	1250	8212	5081
							2828	1201	8250	5012	1881	0118	8182
							5050	1812	0181	8118	2882	1228	8201
							8181	2818	1282	8228	5001	1850	0112
							8282	5028	1801	0150	8112	2881	1218
0201	5850	2112	0881	8818	5282	2028	0102	8152	2808	1258	8220	5088	1821
0812	8881	5218	2082	0228	5801	2150	1208	8258	5020	1888	0121	8102	2852
2018	0282	5828	2101	850	8812	5281	1820	0188	8121	2802	1252	8208	5058
2128	0801	8850	5212	2081	0218	5882	2821	1202	8252	5008	1858	0120	8188
5250	2012	0281	5818	2182	828	8801	5052	1808	0158	8120	2888	1221	8202
5881	2118	0882	8828	5201	2050	0212	8158	2820	1288	8221	5002	1852	0108
8882	5228	2001	0250	5812	2181	0818	8288	5021	1802	0152	8108	2858	1220

Back

0105	8151	2810	1280	8215	5085	1825	0205	8810	2015	2125	5251	5880	8885
1210	8280	5015	1885	0125	8105	2851	5851	8880	0285	0805	2010	2115	5225
1815	0185	8125	2805	1251	8210	5080	2110	5215	5825	8851	0280	885	2005
2825	1205	8251	5010	1880	0115	8185	0880	2085	2105	5210	5815	8825	0251
5051	1810	0180	8115	2885	1225	8205	8815	0225	0851	2080	2185	5205	5810
8180	2815	1285	8225	5005	1851	0110	5285	5805	8810	0215	0825	2051	2180
8285	5025	1805	0151	8110	2880	1215	2025	2151	5280	5885	8805	0210	0815
0505	8051	2510	1080	8515	5185	1525							
1010	8580	5115	1585	0525	8005	2551							
1515	0585	8025	2505	1051	8510	5180							
2525	1005	8551	5110	1580	0515	8085							
5151	1510	0580	8015	2585	1025	8505							
8080	2515	1085	8525	5105	1551	0510							
8585	5125	1505	0551	8010	2580	1015							

Above magic cube is **universal**, i.e., each face is **upside-down** and **mirror looking**.

6 Universal and Upside-down Magic Cubes of Order 8

6.1 Upside-down Magic Cubes

Example 6.1. *Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 8:*

1198	8806	6861	0169	6618	9986	8990	1610	1098	8606	6961	0669	6118	9886	9090	1810	1099	8601	6966	0668	6116	9888	9089	1811
6610	9990	8986	1618	1169	8861	6806	0198	6110	9890	9086	1818	1069	8661	6906	0698	6111	9889	9088	1816	1068	8666	6901	0699
0106	6898	8869	1161	1686	8918	9910	6690	0606	6998	8669	1061	1886	9018	9810	6190	0601	6999	8668	1066	1888	9016	9811	6189
1690	8910	9918	6686	0161	6869	8898	1106	1890	9010	9818	6186	0661	6969	8698	1006	1889	9011	9816	6188	0666	6968	8699	1001
6886	0118	1110	8890	8906	1698	6669	9961	6986	0618	1010	8690	9006	1898	6169	9861	6988	0616	1011	8689	9001	1899	6168	9866
8961	1669	6698	9906	6890	0110	1118	8886	9061	1869	6198	9806	6990	0610	1018	8686	9066	1868	6199	9801	6989	0611	1016	8688
8818	1186	0190	6810	9998	6606	1661	8969	8618	1086	0690	6910	9898	6106	1861	9069	8616	1088	0689	6911	9899	6101	1866	9068
9969	6661	1606	8998	8810	1190	0186	6818	9869	6161	1806	9098	8610	1090	0686	6918	9868	6166	1801	9099	8611	1089	0688	6916
1199	8801	6866	0168	6616	9988	8989	1611	1096	8608	6960	0680	6119	9881	9091	1809	1196	8808	6860	0180	6619	9981	8991	1609
6611	9989	8988	1616	1168	8866	6801	0199	6109	9891	9081	1819	1080	8660	6908	0696	6609	9991	8981	1619	1180	8860	6808	0196
0101	6899	8868	1166	1688	8916	9911	6689	0608	6996	8680	1060	1881	9019	9809	6191	0108	6896	8880	1160	1681	8919	9909	6691
1689	8911	9916	6688	0166	6868	8899	1101	1891	9009	9819	6181	0660	6980	8696	1008	1691	8909	9919	6681	0160	6880	8896	1108
6888	0116	1111	8889	8901	1699	6668	9966	6981	0619	1009	8691	9008	1896	6180	9860	6881	0119	1109	8891	8908	1696	6680	9960
8966	1668	6699	9901	6889	0111	1116	8888	9060	1880	6196	9808	6991	0609	1019	8681	8960	1680	6696	9908	6891	0109	1119	8881
8816	1188	0189	6811	9999	6601	1666	8968	8619	1081	0691	6909	9896	6108	1860	9080	8819	1181	0191	6809	9996	6608	1660	8980
9968	6666	1601	8999	8811	1189	0188	6816	9880	6160	1808	9096	8609	1091	0681	6919	9980	6660	1608	8996	8809	1191	0181	6819

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 5-digits, 0, 1, 6, 8 and 9. All the blocks of order 8×8 are magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{8 \times 8}(1) := 44238, S_{8 \times 8}(2) := 44238, S_{8 \times 8}(3) := 44238, S_{8 \times 8}(4) := 44238, S_{8 \times 8}(5) := 44244 \text{ and } S_{8 \times 8}(6) := 44244.$$

Interesting, here out of six first four are of equal sums and last two are also of equal sums.

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

								1198	8806	6861	0169	6618	9986	8990	1610
								6610	9990	8986	1618	1169	8861	6806	0198
								0106	6898	8869	1161	1686	8918	9910	6690
								1690	8910	9918	6686	0161	6869	8898	1106
								6886	0118	1110	8890	8906	1698	6669	9961
								8961	1669	6698	9906	6890	0110	1118	8886
								8818	1186	0190	6810	9998	6606	1661	8969
								9969	6661	1606	8998	8810	1190	0186	6818
1099	8601	6966	0668	6116	9888	9089	1811	1098	8606	6961	0669	6118	9886	9090	1810
6111	9889	9088	1816	1068	8666	6901	0699	6110	9890	9086	1818	1069	8661	6906	0698
0601	6999	8668	1066	1888	9016	9811	6189	0606	6998	8669	1061	1886	9018	9810	6190
1889	9011	9816	6188	0666	6968	8699	1001	1890	9010	9818	6186	0661	6969	8698	1006
6988	0616	1011	8689	9001	1899	6168	9866	6986	0618	1010	8690	9006	1898	6169	9861
9066	1868	6199	9801	6989	0611	1016	8688	9061	1869	6198	9806	6990	0610	1018	8686
8616	1088	0689	6911	9899	6101	1866	9068	8618	1086	0690	6910	9898	6106	1861	9069
9868	6166	1801	9099	8611	1089	0688	6916	9869	6161	1806	9098	8610	1090	0686	6918

Back

1199	8801	6866	0168	6616	9988	8989	1611	1096	8608	6960	0680	6119	9881	9091	1809
6611	9989	8988	1616	1168	8866	6801	0199	6109	9891	9081	1819	1080	8660	6908	0696
0101	6899	8868	1166	1688	8916	9911	6689	0608	6996	8680	1060	1881	9019	9809	6191
1689	8911	9916	6688	0166	6868	8899	1101	1891	9009	9819	6181	0660	6980	8696	1008
6888	0116	1111	8889	8901	1699	6668	9966	6981	0619	1009	8691	9008	1896	6180	9860
8966	1668	6699	9901	6889	0111	1116	8888	9060	1880	6196	9808	6991	0609	1019	8681
8816	1188	0189	6811	9999	6601	1666	8968	8619	1081	691	6909	9896	6108	1860	9080
9968	6666	1601	8999	8811	1189	0188	6816	9880	6160	1808	9096	8609	1091	0681	6919
1196	8808	6860	0180	6619	9981	8991	1609								
6609	9991	8981	1619	1180	8860	6808	0196								
0108	6896	8880	1160	1681	8919	9909	6691								
1691	8909	9919	6681	0160	6880	8896	1108								
6881	0119	1109	8891	8908	1696	6680	9960								
8960	1680	6696	9908	6891	0109	1119	8881								
8819	1181	0191	6809	9996	6608	1660	8980								
9980	6660	1608	8996	8809	1191	0181	6819								

Above magic cube is **upside-down**, i.e., each face is 180° rotatable.

Example 6.2. *Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 8:*

5598	8826	6865	2569	6658	9986	8992	5652	5298	8626	6965	2669	6558	9886	9292	5852	5299	8625	6966	2668	6556	9888	9289	5855
6652	9992	8986	5658	5569	8865	6826	2598	6552	9892	9286	5858	5269	8665	6926	2698	6555	9889	9288	5856	5268	8666	6925	2699
2526	6898	8869	5565	5686	8958	9952	6692	2626	6998	8669	5265	5886	9258	9852	6592	2625	6999	8668	5266	5888	9256	9855	6589
5692	8952	9958	6686	2565	6869	8898	5526	5892	9252	9858	6586	2665	6969	8698	5226	5889	9255	9856	6588	2666	6968	8699	5225
6886	2558	5552	8892	8926	5698	6669	9965	6986	2658	5252	8692	9226	5898	6569	9865	6988	2656	5255	8689	9225	5899	6568	9866
8965	5669	6698	9926	6892	2552	5558	8886	9265	5869	6598	9826	6992	2652	5258	8686	9266	5868	6599	9825	6989	2655	5256	8688
8858	5586	2592	6852	9998	6626	5665	8969	8658	5286	2692	6952	9898	6526	5865	9269	8656	5288	2689	6955	9899	6525	5866	9268
9969	6665	5626	8998	8852	5592	2586	6858	9869	6565	5826	9298	8652	5292	2686	6958	9868	6566	5825	9299	8655	5289	2688	6956
5599	8825	6866	2568	6656	9988	8989	5655	5296	8628	6962	2682	6559	9885	9295	5829	5596	8828	6862	2582	6659	9985	8995	5629
6655	9989	8988	5656	5568	8866	6825	2599	6529	9895	9285	5859	5282	8662	6928	2696	6629	9995	8985	5659	5582	8862	6828	2596
2525	6899	8868	5566	5688	8956	9955	6689	628	6996	8682	5262	5885	9259	9829	6595	2528	6896	8882	5562	5685	8959	9929	6695
5689	8955	9956	6688	2566	6868	8899	5525	5895	9229	9859	6585	2662	6982	8696	5228	5695	8929	9959	6685	2562	6882	8896	5528
6888	2556	5555	8889	8925	5699	6668	9966	6985	2659	5229	8695	9228	5896	6582	9862	6885	2559	5529	8895	8928	5696	6682	9962
8966	5668	6699	9925	6889	2555	5556	8888	9262	5882	6596	9828	6995	2629	5259	8685	8962	5682	6696	9928	6895	2529	5559	8885
8856	5588	2589	6855	9999	6625	5666	8968	8659	5285	2695	6929	9896	6528	5862	9282	8859	5585	2595	6829	9996	6628	5662	8982
9968	6666	5625	8999	8855	5589	2588	6856	9882	6562	5828	9296	8629	5295	2685	6959	9982	6662	5628	8996	8829	5595	2585	6859

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 5-digits, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9. All the blocks of order 8x8 are magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{8 \times 8}(1) := 55146, S_{8 \times 8}(2) := 55146, S_{8 \times 8}(3) := 55146, S_{8 \times 8}(4) := 55146, S_{8 \times 8}(5) := 55136 \text{ and } S_{8 \times 8}(6) := 55136.$$

Interesting, here out of six first four are of equal sums and last two are also of equal sums.

*Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.*

Front

								5598	8826	6865	2569	6658	9986	8992	5652
								6652	9992	8986	5658	5569	8865	6826	2598
								2526	6898	8869	5565	5686	8958	9952	6692
								5692	8952	9958	6686	2565	6869	8898	5526
								6886	2558	5552	8892	8926	5698	6669	9965
								8965	5669	6698	9926	6892	2552	5558	8886
								8858	5586	592	6852	9998	6626	5665	8969
								9969	6665	5626	8998	8852	5592	586	6858
5299	8625	6966	2668	6556	9888	9289	5855	5298	8626	6965	2669	6558	9886	9292	5852
6555	9889	9288	5856	5268	8666	6925	2699	6552	9892	9286	5858	5269	8665	6926	2698
2625	6999	8668	5266	5888	9256	9855	6589	2626	6998	8669	5265	5886	9258	9852	6592
5889	9255	9856	6588	2666	6968	8699	5225	5892	9252	9858	6586	2665	6969	8698	5226
6988	2656	5255	8689	9225	5899	6568	9866	6986	2658	5252	8692	9226	5898	6569	9865
9266	5868	6599	9825	6989	2655	5256	8688	9265	5869	6598	9826	6992	2652	5258	8686
8656	5288	2689	6955	9899	6525	5866	9268	8658	5286	2692	6952	9898	6526	5865	9269
9868	6566	5825	9299	8655	5289	2688	6956	9869	6565	5826	9298	8652	5292	2686	6958

Back

5599	8825	6866	2568	6656	9988	8989	5655	5296	8628	6962	2682	6559	9885	9295	5829
6655	9989	8988	5656	5568	8866	6825	2599	6529	9895	9285	5859	5282	8662	6928	2696
2525	6899	8868	5566	5688	8956	9955	6689	2628	6996	8682	5262	5885	9259	9829	6595
5689	8955	9956	6688	2566	6868	8899	5525	5895	9229	9859	6585	2662	6982	8696	5228
6888	2556	5555	8889	8925	5699	6668	9966	6985	2659	5229	8695	9228	5896	6582	9862
8966	5668	6699	9925	6889	2555	5556	8888	9262	5882	6596	9828	6995	2629	5259	8685
8856	5588	2589	6855	9999	6625	5666	8968	8659	5285	2695	6929	9896	6528	5862	9282
9968	6666	5625	8999	8855	5589	2588	6856	9882	6562	5828	9296	8629	5295	2685	6959
5596	8828	6862	2582	6659	9985	8995	5629								
6629	9995	8985	5659	5582	8862	6828	2596								
2528	6896	8882	5562	5685	8959	9929	6695								
5695	8929	9959	6685	2562	6882	8896	5528								
6885	2559	5529	8895	8928	5696	6682	9962								
8962	5682	6696	9928	6895	2529	5559	8885								
8859	5585	2595	6829	9996	6628	5662	8982								
9982	6662	5628	8996	8829	5595	2585	6859								

Above magic cube is **upside-down**, i.e., each face is 180° rotatable.

6.2 Universal Magic Cube

Example 6.3. *Let's consider the following six magic squares of order 8:*

5518	8820	0805	2501	0058	1180	8112	5052	5218	8020	0105	2001	0558	1880	1212	5852	5211	8025	0100	2008	0550	1888	1281	5855
0052	1112	8180	5058	5501	8805	0820	2518	0552	1812	1280	5858	5201	8005	0120	2018	0555	1881	1288	5850	5208	8000	0125	2011
2520	0818	8801	5505	5080	8158	1152	0012	2020	0118	8001	5205	5880	1258	1852	0512	2025	0111	8008	5200	5888	1250	1855	0581
5012	8152	1158	0080	2505	0801	8818	5520	5812	1252	1858	0580	2005	0101	8018	5220	5881	1255	1850	0588	2000	0108	8011	5225
0880	2558	5552	8812	8120	5018	0001	1105	0180	2058	5252	8012	1220	5818	0501	1805	0188	2050	5255	8081	1225	5811	0508	1800
8105	5001	0018	1120	0812	2552	5558	8880	1205	5801	0518	1820	0112	2052	5258	8080	1200	5808	0511	1825	0181	2055	5250	8088
8858	5580	2512	852	118	0020	5005	8101	8058	5280	2012	0152	1818	0520	5805	1201	8050	5288	2081	0155	1811	0525	5800	1208
1101	0005	5020	8118	8852	5512	2580	0858	1801	0505	5820	1218	8052	5212	2080	0158	1808	0500	5825	1211	8055	5281	2088	0150
5511	8825	0800	2508	0050	1188	8181	5055	5210	8028	0102	2082	0551	1885	1215	5821	5510	8828	0802	2582	0051	1185	8115	5021
0055	1181	8188	5050	5508	8800	0825	2511	0521	1815	1285	5851	5282	8002	0128	2010	0021	1115	8185	5051	5582	8802	828	2510
2525	0811	8808	5500	5088	8150	1155	0081	0028	0110	8082	5202	5885	1251	1821	0515	2528	0810	8882	5502	5085	8151	1121	0015
5081	8155	1150	0088	2500	0808	8811	5525	5815	1221	1851	0585	2002	0182	8010	5228	5015	8121	1151	0085	2502	0882	8810	5528
0888	2550	5555	8881	8125	5011	0008	1100	0185	2051	5221	8015	1228	5810	0582	1802	0885	2551	5521	8815	8128	5010	0082	1102
8100	5008	0011	1125	881	2555	5550	8888	1202	5882	0510	1828	0115	2021	5251	8085	8102	5082	0010	1128	8815	2521	5551	8885
8850	5588	2581	0855	1111	0025	5000	8108	8051	5285	2015	0121	1810	0528	5802	1282	8851	5585	2515	0821	1110	0028	5002	8182
1108	0000	5025	8111	8855	5581	2588	0850	1882	0502	5828	1210	8021	5215	2085	0151	1182	0002	5028	8110	8821	5515	2585	0851

The above six magic squares are constructed using only 5-digits, 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8. All the blocks of order 8×8 are magic squares with different magic sums, i.e.,

$$S_{8 \times 8}(1) := 32046, S_{8 \times 8}(2) := 24846, S_{8 \times 8}(3) := 24918, S_{8 \times 8}(4) := 32118, S_{8 \times 8}(5) := 32118 \text{ and } S_{8 \times 8}(6) := 32094.$$

Let's divide the structure of **magic cube** in two parts. One as front side and another as back side. In the both case, there are three magic squares.

Front

								0052	1112	8180	5058	5501	8805	0820	2518
								2520	0818	8801	5505	5080	8158	1152	0012
								5012	8152	1158	0080	2505	0801	8818	5520
								0880	2558	5552	8812	8120	5018	0001	1105
								8105	5001	0018	1120	0812	2552	5558	8880
								8858	5580	0512	0852	1118	0020	5005	8101
								1101	0005	5020	8118	8852	5512	0580	0858
5211	8025	0100	2008	0550	1888	1281	5855	5218	8020	0105	2001	0558	1880	1212	5852
0555	1881	1288	5850	5208	8000	0125	2011	0552	1812	1280	5858	5201	8005	0120	2018
2025	0111	8008	5200	5888	1250	1855	0581	2020	0118	8001	5205	5880	1258	1852	0512
5881	1255	1850	0588	2000	0108	8011	5225	5812	1252	1858	0580	2005	0101	8018	5220
0188	2050	5255	8081	1225	5811	0508	1800	0180	2058	5252	8012	1220	5818	0501	1805
1200	5808	0511	1825	0181	2055	5250	8088	1205	5801	0518	1820	0112	2052	5258	8080
8050	5288	2081	0155	1811	0525	5800	1208	8058	5280	2012	0152	1818	0520	5805	1201
1808	0500	5825	1211	8055	5281	2088	0150	1801	0505	5820	1218	8052	5212	2080	0158

Back

5511	8825	0800	2508	0050	1188	8181	5055	5210	8028	0102	2082	0551	1885	1215	5821
0055	1181	8188	5050	5508	8800	0825	2511	0521	1815	1285	5851	5282	8002	0128	2010
2525	0811	8808	5500	5088	8150	1155	0081	2028	0110	8082	5202	5885	1251	1821	0515
5081	8155	1150	0088	2500	0808	8811	5525	5815	1221	1851	0585	2002	0182	8010	5228
0888	2550	5555	8881	8125	5011	0008	1100	0185	2051	5221	8015	1228	5810	0582	1802
8100	5008	0011	1125	0881	2555	5550	8888	1202	5882	0510	1828	0115	2021	5251	8085
8850	5588	2581	0855	1111	0025	5000	8108	8051	5285	2015	0121	1810	0528	5802	1282
1108	0000	5025	8111	8855	5581	2588	0850	1882	0502	5828	1210	8021	5215	2085	0151
5510	8828	0802	2582	0051	1185	8115	5021								
0021	1115	8185	5051	5582	8802	0828	2510								
2528	0810	8882	5502	5085	8151	1121	0015								
5015	8121	1151	0085	2502	0882	8810	5528								
0885	2551	5521	8815	8128	5010	0082	1102								
8102	5082	0010	1128	0815	2521	5551	8885								
8851	5585	2515	0821	1110	0028	5002	8182								
1182	0002	5028	8110	8821	5515	2585	0851								

Above magic cube is **upside-down**, i.e., each face is 180° rotatable.

7 Author's Contributions to Magic Squares

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 1. <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
 2. <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 1. <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>
 2. <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>

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- [1] **C. Boyer**, Multimagic Squares, <http://www.multimagie.com>.
 - [2] **O.A. Dawood, A.M.S. Rahma and A. M.J. A.Hossen**, Generalized Method for Constructing Magic Cube by Folded Magic Squares, *I.J. Intelligent Systems and Applications*, 2016, 1, 1-8, Published Online January 2016 in MECS (<http://www.mecs-press.org/>), DOI: 10.5815/ijisa.2016.01.01. Also refer <https://shorturl.at/pzqOP>.
 - [3] **B. Golunski**, <http://www.number-galaxy.eu/>
 - [4] **W. Trump**, Perfect Magic Cubes, <https://shorturl.at/lyL3R>
 - [5] **W. Trump**, New Discoveries in the History of Magic Cubes, <https://shorturl.at/qXwCh>
 - [6] **W. Walkington** Magic Box Cubes, Rubik's Cubes and Twisty Puzzles, <https://shorturl.at/EaQRy>
 - [7] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
 - [8] **A. Winkel**, The Magic Encyclopedia, <http://magichypercubes.com/Encyclopedia/>
- **Block-Wise Magic Squares**
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
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- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.

• Bordered Magic Squares

- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.
- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.
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